

Real-time, non-invasive analysis of biocatalytic PET degradation

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Supplementary Figures

Fig.S1: Geometry of the 3D-printed polypropylene insert. **A** Top, frontal, side and back views from the insert and cross sections. PET window ($4.7 \times 9.5 \text{ mm}^2$) is $4.3 \times 9.1 \text{ mm}^2$ after printing with a 0.4 nozzle on an Ultimaker 3.0 Extended. **B** Cura 4.8 preview of the sliced insert. Numerical data in mm.

Fig.S2: Impedance spectrum of an “open” reaction window. Dash line marks base resistance of the measurement system of 90Ω ($= R_1$). Impedance spectra was fitted to an equivalent circuit model of a double-layer capacitance C_{dl} in series with a resistance R_1 . C_{dl} was determined to be $5.63 \mu\text{F}$, which is five orders of magnitude higher compared to the case of a “PET-closed” reaction window. Thus, its contribution to the impedance signal during a PET-degradation experiment is negligible. Mean \pm sd ($n = 4$)

Fig.S3: Change in capacitance with and without PHL7. Data for G-PET film hydrolysis with $13.9 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ PHL7 (green graphs) and negative control without enzyme present (blue graphs) are shown.

Figure S4: Determination of the G-PET film capacitance using inserts with variable PET windows at 70°C in enzyme-free reaction buffer. **A** PP inserts with different sized reaction windows, specified with size factor to the original insert. **B** Capacitance of the PET film in the reaction setup was determined at 5.1 pF by a linear regression. This value fitted well with a theoretically calculated value, assuming a slightly higher relative permittivity of 3.3 (70°C), compared with the manufacturer’s specification of 3.0 (25°C) in accordance with the temperature difference. The change in size of the PET reaction window caused also a slight change in the size of the PP insert and thus C_{rest} .

Figure S5: FEM simulation of PET film. The PET film was simulated with dimensions of 4.3 x 9.1 mm², a thickness of 225 µm and a relative permittivity of 3.3 (left). The derived impedance magnitude spectrum correlates well with the experimental data (right).

Fig.S6: Translation of the capacitance into G-PET film thickness. **A** Capacitance determined by an equivalent circuit model. **B** Pure capacitance change over time. **C** Calculated film thickness using a default value of the PET film derived by mechanical measurement.

Figure S7: FEM simulation for investigation of surface increase effect on PET film capacitance. **A** To overcome computation limits, the simulation was performed with PET film dimensions of 1 x 1 mm². The initial PET film thickness was set to 80 μm according to the final optical/mechanical measurements after 10 h (see Fig. 2A). The surface area was increased by 5 %, 10 % and 15 % while keeping the maximum film thickness at 80 μm (cross section, scale bar = 100 μm). **B** The FEM simulation derived

impedance magnitude spectra revealed the surface increase dependent decrease of the impedance magnitude. **C** Based on the FEM simulation derived impedance magnitude spectra, the PET film capacitance was determined by equivalent circuit fitting (simulated area of $1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^2$). Furthermore, the capacitance of the measured PET film ($4.3 \times 9.1 \text{ mm}^2$) as well as the capacitance ratio was calculated.

Fig.S8: Surface of the G-PET film after 2.5 h degradation by PHL7 analyzed by intermittent-contact atomic force microscopy. Especially in regions of depressions at the bottom of degradation craters, a high content of low roughness and low curvature areas were detected (arrows). Squares marked in green in the upper left image show enlarged areas. Height scales range from zero to the value indicated in the upper right corner of each image in nm. 1b and 3b show enlarged areas (dashed squares) of the lock-in phase signal of the corresponding height image.

Fig. S9: Degradation of R-PET film from a post-consumer PET thermoform clamshell packing and a G-PET film. Blue: R-PET, green: G-PET. Squares mark thickness values of the mechanical measurement, while circles mark thickness values derived from impedance data. In case of the R-PET film, three distinct degradation time zones could be observed. Especially noticeable is zone b, where a particularly slow degradation took place after a very high apparent thickness decrease in zone a. In contrast, the G-PET film only sparsely showed a zone formation.

Fig. S10: Deviation in time until pore formation of G-PET film degraded with $27.6 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ PHL7. Six samples were run simultaneously and deviated only by a maximum of 20 min in the first pore formation event. Four of the six samples deviated only by ± 1 min. Left: Overview of the change in R2 over time, Right: Close-up of the breakthrough time.

Figure S11: FEM simulation based analysis of solvent conductivity influence on the PET film capacitance. The PET film was simulated with dimensions of $4.3 \times 9.1 \text{ mm}^2$, and thickness of $225 \mu\text{m}$ (left) as well as $12 \mu\text{m}$ (right), a relative permittivity of 3.3 and different solvent conductivities according to the experimental evaluated potassium phosphate buffer concentration of 0.1 M ($1.7 \text{ S}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$), 0.3 M ($4.5 \text{ S}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$), 1 M ($11 \text{ S}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$), 2 M ($16 \text{ S}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$) (see Fig. 3C). The conductivity of the used buffer solutions was determined with a SevenExcellence pH/Cond/Do meter S479-K and the Cond probe InLab 738 ISM (Mettler Toledo, USA). From the FEM simulation derived impedance magnitude spectra, the appropriate capacitances (shown in brackets) were determined by equivalent circuit fitting.

Figure S12: Time dependent increase of Pore 1 diameter. FEM simulation were performed for one pore with an increase in pore diameter to fit the impedance spectra derived R2 values according to the experimental data set of the black graph in Fig.4A. Due to the occurrence of a second pore after 17 s, the fitted data of the first 15 s were used for fitting and calculation of the diameter of Pore 1 for the following time points.

Figure S13: FEM simulation of multiple pore formations. The PET film was simulated with dimensions of $4.3 \times 9.1 \text{ mm}^2$ and a thickness of $12 \mu\text{m}$ according to the equivalent circuit derived capacitance at the time of pore formation. Current density for 1.26 kHz at distinct times after first detected pore formation event are shown with pore diameters in brackets.